

OPEN ACCESS

Journal of Business and Economic Analysis, Vol. 7, No. 2 (2025) 48-75

© UBD School of Business and Economics

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17636276>

Digital vs. Traditional Marketing for E-Businesses in Brunei: Comparing Effectiveness for Food & Beverage Consumers

NUR AN'UMILLAH MD BOESTAMAN, NUR AMANINA BINTI ABD MUTALIB, HIDAYATUL AQEILLAH BINTI ABDULLAH, MOHAMMAD NORESWANDY, MAS FATIN NADHIRAH MAHDINI, HIDAYATI BINTI OMAR SHARIFF, NUR RAHELA SHAFEZZA SHAFREE, MOHAMMAD NABIL ALMUNAWAR^{‡*}

*UBD School of Business and Economics
Universiti Brunei Darussalam, Brunei Darussalam
‡nabil.almunawar@ubd.edu.bn*

Received 10 June 2025

Revised 28 July 2025

Revised 9 August 2025

Accepted 8 September 2025

Published 18 November 2025

Abstract

Recently, many companies have rapidly shifted their marketing strategies from traditional to digital. However, traditional marketing has not been entirely replaced; it remains effective for promoting products and services to certain market segments. This study aims to identify the best marketing method between traditional and digital approaches, to find the best reach and engage the target audience by analysing the effects of both tactics on food and beverage consumers in Brunei Darussalam. Using a quantitative method approach, the data was collected through consumer surveys and analysis of previous case studies in Brunei. The study reveals that traditional marketing is still helpful in reaching specific groups, but digital marketing is more effective at attracting consumer interest because it is interactive. This suggests that integrating traditional and digital marketing strategies may help increase brand recognition among a range of groups, allowing companies to maximize their reach and engagement.

Key Words: *Digital Marketing, Traditional Marketing, Brunei, E-business, Consumer Engagement*

* Corresponding author

1. Introduction

Marketing is a fundamental business function responsible for creating, promoting, and delivering products or services to both current and potential consumers. It involves delivering the right products, services, or ideas to the right people, at the right place, time, and price, using appropriate promotional techniques, while also providing consumer support related to those services. Modern marketing management philosophy revolves around the idea that “the customer is king” — implies that every decision, whether direct or indirect, is shaped by consumer needs. From production and design to the transportation of goods, each step is focused on ensuring consumer satisfaction (Kalmegh, 2022).

Traditional marketing, the most familiar form of marketing, refers to non-digital methods used to promote a company’s products or services (Yasmin et al., 2015). It encompasses a broad range of advertising and marketing techniques, including print media, broadcast media, and outdoor advertising. Historically, traditional marketing has been used to inform the public about products or services available for purchase. While it remains effective for reaching traditional audiences, the widespread adoption of digital devices such as smartphones, has made it increasingly challenging for companies to stay competitive using only traditional methods (Kalmegh, 2022).

In contrast, digital marketing refers to the promotion of products or services through digital platforms to engage with consumers (Yasmin et al., 2015). It leverages a variety of digital tools and platforms to reach consumers where they spend most of their time — online (Sinha, 2018). This approach combines strategies such as content marketing, influencer marketing, search engine optimization, social media, and online advertising to attract, engage, and convert consumers in a digital environment. Digital marketing also allows brands to monitor the effectiveness of their efforts in real time providing valuable data-driven insights.

Marketing plays a critical role in attracting consumers and persuading them to engage in business transactions. Understanding consumer behaviour is essential as it enables companies to tailor their approaches and communicate more effectively. In recent years, innovative marketing strategies and advanced technologies for collecting consumer data have allowed businesses to better understand their consumers and engage with them more efficiently and effectively (Ahamat et al., 2022).

The rapid rise of digital marketing has transformed how businesses reach and engage consumers. Many foods and beverages (F&B) companies in Brunei continue to rely on traditional marketing strategies to attract consumers, however, they are beginning to adopt digital methods. While digital marketing offers advantages such as greater reach, real-time interaction, and data-driven insights, traditional marketing remains relevant to reach local, non-digital-savvy audiences. This dual approach raises questions about which strategy drives better results for F&B consumers in Brunei. By integrating social media into F&B business operations, it may help promote their offerings, manage their reputations, and engage diverse market segments to boost their visibility (Billore & Sadh, 2015). This approach serves as a powerful marketing tool aiding businesses in achieving business objectives, building relationships, and earning consumer loyalty and trust through feedback (Jaman et al., 2020).

Businesses should consider incorporating social media into their strategies to access substantial benefits which can enhance their connections with both suppliers (Supplier Relationship Management) and consumers (Customer Relationship Management), allowing them to update products or services and manage marketing activities via social platforms (Cesaroni and Consoli, 2015). Social usage is believed to help expand the consumer base and support product sales through digital channels contributing to increased profits (Gongora, 2016).

This research aims to evaluate and compare the effectiveness of digital versus traditional marketing strategies in driving consumer engagement, sales, and loyalty for F&B e-businesses in Brunei. By understanding which approach yields better results, local businesses can allocate their marketing resources more efficiently. The study provides an in-depth comparison of digital and traditional marketing strategies in Brunei, assessing their impact on consumer behaviour, preferences, and brand awareness.

The research will offer valuable insights into the current state of both digital and traditional marketing in Brunei along with recommendations on strategies that are likely to deliver greater benefits for businesses. It explores Bruneian consumers' preferences and behaviours in relation to their interactions with both digital and traditional marketing. It also examines how consumers perceive various marketing initiatives, including brand loyalty, purchasing behaviours, and overall satisfaction. The findings will enable business organizations to better understand consumer preferences, navigate the ever-evolving marketing landscape, and maximise the effectiveness of their marketing strategies. To achieve these objectives, the research addresses the following

questions: 1) What factors influence consumer preference for digital marketing over traditional marketing, or vice versa? 2) How effective are different marketing strategies in achieving brand awareness and consumer engagement within the F&B sector?

The rest of the paper is organised as follows. Section 2 comprises of the literature reviews covering Brunei as research context, digital marketing in the F&B sector, traditional marketing strategies, consumer preferences between digital and traditional marketing, effectiveness of marketing strategies, consumer satisfaction, brand awareness, the influence of marketing on purchase intention, and the relevant theoretical frameworks with their implications. Section 3 outlines the research framework, and the hypotheses derived from it. Section 4 details the research methodology employed in this study, while Section 5 presents the data analysis and key findings. Section 6 provides an in-depth discussion of the main findings. Finally, Section 7 concludes the study by summarising the findings and highlighting its limitations, followed by Section 8 which offers recommendations for future research.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Brunei as Research Context

Social media significantly impacts the daily lives of Bruneians, with 86% of the population actively using it (Othman, 2017). According to a 2019 survey by the Authority of Infocommunications Technology Industry (AITI), a total of 44% businesses use social media for marketing activities. The 2019 AITI survey found daily that 80% of Bruneians use WhatsApp, followed by Facebook at 31% and Instagram at 28%. Brunei could harness social media as a means of communication and marketing to modernise traditional practices, stay competitive and access a broader market.

Businesses can leverage this trend to quickly reach a broader audience offering a faster and more adaptable approach to achieving business goals compared to traditional marketing methods (Jaman et al., 2020). Social media adoption allows businesses to broadcast updates or announcements on their pages, facilitating two-way communication as consumers can provide feedback and ask questions. In Brunei, many SMEs particularly in the F&B sector, rely on social media for marketing their products or services (Jaman et al., 2020).

2.2 Digital Marketing in the F&B Sector

Digital marketing has become a pivotal force in transforming the F&B industry, offering innovative strategies that significantly enhance consumer engagement. As businesses increasingly embrace digital channels, platforms such as social media, search engines, and email marketing have emerged as crucial tools to reach potential consumers. According to Mkansi (2020), the evolution towards digital marketing has been marked by a notable shift in consumer behaviour, where individuals seek instant gratification and interactive experiences with brands. This paradigm shift enables businesses to leverage real-time data analytics, allowing for targeted marketing efforts that are tailored to individual preferences.

Moreover, effective engagement strategies such as influencer partnerships, interactive content, and personalised advertising, have been shown to drive consumer loyalty and increase sales, particularly among younger demographics (Chaffey, 2020). Ahmad and Omar (2021) emphasise the effectiveness of these digital strategies in the F&B sector, indicating that platforms like Instagram and Facebook play a crucial role in fostering consumer relationships and enhancing brand visibility.

2.3 Traditional Marketing Strategies

Despite the rapid adoption of digital marketing, traditional marketing methods continue to hold significant value within the F&B industry particularly to reach wider consumer demographics. This is supported by Hussein (2019), who highlights that traditional media channels, such as television, radio, print advertising, and billboards, offer a sense of familiarity and reliability that resonates with consumers who may be less engaged with digital platforms. These channels are particularly effective in building brand recall and trust which are critical factors influencing purchase decisions (Tan et al., 2022). For example, in rural areas where internet access may be limited, television advertisements remain a trusted source of information for consumers, reinforcing the brand's presence and credibility. Furthermore, traditional marketing strategies often evoke emotional connections, leveraging storytelling and cultural relevance to resonate with target audiences. Understanding the interplay between digital and traditional approaches is essential for F&B businesses aiming to create holistic marketing strategies that cater to diverse consumer preferences.

2.4 Consumer Preferences: Digital vs Traditional

The preferences of consumers for digital versus traditional marketing strategies reflect broader trends in media consumption and engagement. Younger consumers, particularly those belonging to Generation Z and Millennials, increasingly favour digital marketing platforms due to their interactive and changing features. Research indicates that these consumers are drawn to platforms that offer personalisation, immediacy, and ease of access (Chen & Low, 2020). Conversely, older generations, such as Generation X and Baby Boomers, tend to exhibit a preference for traditional marketing channels, often viewing them as more trustworthy and established (Ahmad & Omar, 2021). This divergence in consumer preferences is influenced by various factors including convenience, the level of engagement offered by different marketing platforms, and the degree of familiarity with digital technology. For instance, while younger consumers may engage with brands through social media, older consumers may prefer the familiarity of print advertisements or television commercials. This dynamic creates a complex landscape where F&B markets must carefully balance their strategies to effectively reach and resonate with diverse consumer segments.

2.5 Effectiveness of Marketing Strategies

The effectiveness of marketing strategies in the F&B sector can be assessed through comparative analyses of digital and traditional marketing channels. Digital marketing has been shown to deliver higher returns on investment (ROI) due to its ability to reach target audiences with precision and cost-effectiveness (Zain & Rosli, 2021). The advent of advanced analytics and data-driven marketing has enabled businesses to tailor their campaigns to specific consumer segments resulting in enhanced engagement and conversion rates. In contrast, traditional marketing, while often more costly, remains effective in establishing brand recognition and trust, particularly among the demographic that values face-to-face interactions (Chen & Low, 2020). For example, brands that utilise television and radio advertising can benefit from broad reach and established credibility which can be crucial in fostering consumer loyalty in regions with limited digital penetration. The challenge for marketers lies in understanding the distinct advantages of each approach and developing integrated marketing strategies that leverage both digital and traditional methods to maximise effectiveness in reaching target audiences.

2.6 *Consumer Satisfaction with Marketing*

Consumer satisfaction refers to how satisfied consumers are with the marketing strategies used by F&B businesses. Digital marketing tends to boost consumer satisfaction due to its personalisation and interactivity. However, traditional marketing, especially in Brunei, enhances more trust (Kotler *et al.*, 2019).

A key indicator of marketing strategy effectiveness is consumer satisfaction, especially in the F&B industry where traditional and digital marketing approaches may yield varied responses. Research indicates that digital marketing, which enables companies to customise messages and communicate directly with consumers, frequently results in greater consumer satisfaction than traditional marketing because of its personalised and interactive elements (Chaffey & Smith, 2017). However, because it uses physical presence to build consumer trust, traditional marketing is still crucial, particularly in culturally distinct situations like Brunei where consumers may prefer familiar, non-digital connections (Kotler *et al.*, 2019). To maximise consumer pleasure and cultivate enduring loyalty, Bruneian F&B companies must comprehend consumer preferences in digital vs traditional formats.

2.7 *Brand Awareness*

Brand awareness is the degree by which consumers acknowledge F&B businesses through marketing strategies whether through digital or traditional marketing. In this study, younger users are more familiar with digital marketing, whereas traditional marketing builds trust among older users (Pappas, 2016).

Traditional and digital marketing significantly impact brand awareness, which is a major factor in consumer decision. Digital marketing has been demonstrated to increase brand visibility by addressing consumers on channels they visit frequently, especially through social media (Pappas, 2016). Among younger, tech-savvy consumers, social media campaigns, SEO and targeted ads are especially successful at building brand recognition (Duffett, 2017). On the other hand, older audiences who are less likely to use digital media can benefit from traditional marketing strategies like print and radio (Solomon *et al.*, 2018). To increase brand awareness among a variety of demographic groups, F&B companies in Brunei can benefit from a combination of traditional and digital marketing strategies.

2.8 Influence of Marketing on Purchase Intention

Both traditional and digital marketing strategies are crucial in influencing consumers' intention to make purchases, particularly in the F&B industry. Digital marketing has been shown to have a favourable impact on consumers' purchasing decisions by generating a sense of urgency and customisation through the provision of timely, relevant, and engaging content (Antczak, 2024).

However, even if they are less focused, traditional marketing techniques can affect consumer intent by creating a feeling of legitimacy and local significance, particularly in Brunei (Batra & Keller, 2016). A balanced approach that accommodates a range of preferences is provided by a mixed marketing strategy, which has been shown to have the greatest potential to influence purchase intention among Bruneian consumers by combining digital urgency and traditional familiarity (Grewal et al., 2018).

2.9 Theoretical Frameworks and Implications

The integration of relevant theoretical frameworks is essential for understanding consumer preferences and the effectiveness of marketing strategies in the F&B sector. The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) positions that consumers' perceptions of the ease of use and perceived usefulness of marketing platforms significantly influence their preferences for digital or traditional marketing (Mkansi, 2020). Engagement Theory (ET) further interprets the role of consumer interaction and engagement with digital marketing, highlighting how social media platforms can foster higher levels of satisfaction and preference compared to traditional channels. Consumer Decision Theory (CDT) examines how marketing messages from both digital and traditional platforms shape consumers' purchase intentions, thereby influencing their overall marketing preferences. By utilising these frameworks, sellers can better understand the independent and dependent variables at play in consumer behaviour, enabling them to develop target strategies that resonate with their audience.

3. Research framework and hypothesis development

Figure 1. Research Framework

3.1. Marketing Effectiveness

The ability of a marketing strategy to produce desirable outcomes such as customer engagement, brand awareness and purchasing intention is measured by marketing effectiveness. This assesses how much traditional, or digital marketing strategies could affect consumer behaviour and would help generate profits. However, for this research it measures marketing success by examining consumer responses (for example, preference) to different marketing strategies used in the Brunei food and beverage industry. The effectiveness of marketing and the impact of marketing channels on consumer purchasing behaviour are closely related, and digital media often applies greater influence through personalisation and interaction (Mehmeti-Bajrami et al., 2022). According to Singh and Bisaria (2024), successful marketing involves assessing how marketing tactics could affect consumer behaviour and engagement across platforms (Singh & Bisaria, 2024).

According to Mehmeti-Bajrami (2022), the study examines various marketing techniques and its impact on consumer purchasing decisions. The research shows that consumers are more influenced by digital media than traditional media. Which means that the effectiveness of digital marketing is positively correlated with consumer preference for digital platforms, in this regard,

consumers tend to prefer more personalised activations that leverage latest technologies such as animation and 3D graphics, making consumers more likely to be influenced and persuaded in their purchasing decisions (Mehmeti-Bajrami, 2022).

Another study by Singh and Bisaria (2024), explores the different marketing strategies and how they influence brands. The study also highlights the power of digital marketing as it relates to changing these dynamics. The study findings grasp the importance of digital marketing when it comes to consumer engagement and preferences. Which proves that it is more effective to reach consumers through digital marketing when they can be more inclined towards using the offered digital platforms than the traditional ones (Singh & Basaria, 2024). We hypothesise that marketing effectiveness (digital vs. traditional) and consumer preference will influence consumer preferences for marketing platforms:

H1a: Digital marketing effectiveness positively influences consumer preferences for digital platforms.

H1b: Traditional marketing effectiveness negatively influences consumer preferences for traditional platforms.

3.2. Purchase Intention

A study by Ismaeel and Alsariera (2023), explores the relationship between marketing effectiveness and consumer behaviour, focusing on how it changes consumer purchasing preferences. Findings show that effective marketing strategies significantly influence consumer preferences, which support that digital platforms have a positive influence on purchase intention. This research reveals that digital marketing has the potential to increase purchase intent (Ismaeel & Alsariera, 2023). The second study conducted by Bukhowa et al. (2024) shows that there is a positive correlation between digital marketing and purchase intention. The study concluded that the nature of digital marketing campaigns, which involves targeting and interacting with consumers at the right time, has made digital platforms preferred over other traditional methods to market to consumers (Bukhowa et al., 2024). We hypothesise that the influence of marketing on purchase intention significantly affects consumer preferences for digital vs. traditional marketing:

H2a: Purchase intention positively influences consumer preference for digital marketing platforms.

H2b: Purchase intention negatively influences consumer preference for traditional marketing platforms.

3.3 Consumer Satisfaction with Marketing and Consumer Preference

A study examined how consumers react to integrated marketing strategies that use both traditional and digital media. Consumers that use both channels have been shown to prefer traditional platforms for some product kinds, such as those that need their physical presence. However, satisfaction with digital convenience can reduce the preference for traditional marketing, demonstrating how digital satisfaction may have a negative effect on their preferences (Rosário & Raimundo, 2021).

Another case study looked at how platform preference and brand loyalty are affected by consumer satisfaction in both traditional and digital marketing contexts. It concluded that while preferences for online purchasing are in line with digital satisfaction, preferences for physical stores are positively impacted by satisfaction with in-store experiences. According to these results, the consumer's perception of the value and satisfaction of each channel has a significant role in determining whether to use digital or traditional platforms (Evangelidis et al, 2024).

We hypothesise that consumer satisfaction with marketing (digital vs. traditional) significantly influences consumer preferences for marketing platforms:

H3a: Consumer satisfaction with digital marketing negatively influences consumer preferences for digital platforms.

H3b: Consumer satisfaction with traditional marketing positively influences consumer preferences for traditional platforms.

3.4 Brand Awareness and Consumer Preference

A study by Qaderi (2022) analysed how consumer preferences for local restaurants were impacted by both traditional and digital brand awareness campaigns. According to the research, social media-based digital brand awareness initiatives improved recognition of brands but did not always lead to a preference for digital platforms. Rather, many consumers, particularly for local businesses, favoured the familiarity and ease of established channels. These consumers' preferences for conventional channels were fostered by traditional media, such as print advertisements in local publications, which were successful in establishing brand trust and loyalty.

Another study examined the effects of several media strategies, such as physical and online advertisements, on Northern Cyprus fast-food consumers' brand recognition and preferences. The study found that traditional media, such as billboards and in-store marketing, more effectively strengthened long-term loyalty, even while internet ads had an influence on raising awareness among younger groups. This result supports the hypothesis that consumers prefer traditional marketing channels for regular brand interactions (Ali Karam & Saydam, 2015).

We hypothesise that brand awareness created by marketing strategies (digital vs. traditional) significantly influences consumer preferences for marketing platforms:

H4a: Brand awareness through digital marketing negatively influences consumer preferences for digital platforms.

H4b: Brand awareness through traditional marketing positively influences consumer preferences for traditional platforms.

4. Research Methodology

4.1. Sample and Data Collection Procedure

Convenience sampling was utilised for this study to gather responses from consumers. This method allows for the efficient collection of data from a readily accessible group of respondents, such as consumers of F&B businesses, who can share their preferences and behaviours regarding digital marketing. While convenience sampling may have limitations in terms of generalisability, it is effective for obtaining quick insights into consumer interactions with marketing channels.

The study gathered 103 respondents from F&B consumers in Brunei through a structured survey, which was distributed by word-of-mouth on social media platforms such as Instagram and WhatsApp. With consideration for time and resource restrictions, this sample size is determined to retain feasibility and achieve statistical significance. By focusing on consumers, the data will provide insights into their interactions with both digital and traditional marketing strategies, as well as provide a thorough understanding of the effectiveness of digital and traditional marketing strategies.

The data collection procedure for this study is conducted through an online survey using Google Forms, an efficient and accessible tool for gathering responses from a large sample of participants. The survey will focus on gathering information about consumer engagement with both digital and traditional marketing methods in the F&B sector. The survey was opened for three

weeks and used convenience sampling to efficiently gather participants. To protect participant confidentiality, all survey responses will be anonymous and kept private.

In addition, a comprehensive literature review was completed to assess the current situation of digital and traditional marketing in Brunei, providing insights into how F&B businesses utilise these channels. This evaluation will identify the most popular marketing methods and platforms, such as Instagram, WhatsApp, and radio, and assess their success in reaching and engaging target consumers in the F&B industry. Furthermore, it will identify gaps in the existing literature, particularly in the context of Brunei, and incorporate these findings into the framework for analysing survey results.

4.2. Item Measurement

The survey utilised a 5-point Likert scale to assess six main constructs: marketing effectiveness, consumer satisfaction, influence on purchasing intention, brand awareness, traditional consumer preferences and digital consumer preferences. This technique seeks to understand consumer behaviours to various marketing strategies in Brunei's F&B business.

Table 1: *Measurement items*

Constructs	items	source
Marketing Effectiveness	1. The digital marketing content of F&B businesses is informative.	Chaffey & Smith (2022)
	2. I find the online advertisements from F&B businesses appealing and creative.	Duffett & Graeme (2017)
	3. A combination of both digital and traditional marketing is more effective in influencing my dining decisions at F&B businesses.	
Consumer Satisfaction	1. I am satisfied with the digital marketing advertisements from F&B businesses.	Pappas (2016) Batra & Keller (2016) Kotler et al. (2019).
	2. The digital advertisements reflect the quality of the products offered by F&B businesses. I am satisfied with the traditional marketing advertisements (TV, radio, print).	

- | | | |
|--|--|---|
| Influence of Marketing on Purchasing Intention | <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. The digital ads of F&B businesses make me more aware of their promotions.2. Digital ads influence my dining decisions more than other digital platforms.3. Word-of-mouth recommendations show that the F&B business is worth trying.4. Positive online reviews and ratings increase the likelihood of visiting an F&B business. | Alalwan (2018)
Yuliantoro et al. (2019b) |
| Brand Awareness | <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. I easily recognize F&B brands that use digital marketing strategies (social media, online ads).2. Frequent exposure to digital ads (e.g., social media) increases my awareness of F&B businesses.3. I easily recognize F&B brands that use traditional marketing strategies (e.g., billboards, TV, flyers).4. Frequent traditional ads (flyers, billboards, TV) improve my perception of a brand's reputation. | Solomon et al. (2024)
Khan et al. (2019) |
| Traditional Consumer Preferences | <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Traditional marketing (TV, radio, print) helps increase my awareness of F&B businesses.2. I have visited a restaurant after seeing its advertisement in a local newspaper, TV, or radio.3. Traditional ads (TV, radio, billboards) are effective in catching my attention.4. I trust traditional marketing (flyers, radio, TV) more than digital marketing when it comes to F&B businesses.5. TV advertisements catch my attention more than other traditional marketing methods.6. I am more likely to visit a restaurant after seeing its ad on a billboard than in a newspaper. | Sama (2019) |

	<ol style="list-style-type: none">7. I tend to visit restaurants after seeing promotions through traditional marketing methods (e.g., TV, billboards, newspapers).8. Traditional advertisements (e.g., banners or billboards) in strategic locations near F&B businesses influence my decision to dine there.	
Digital Consumer Preferences	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. I frequently engage with F&B businesses' social media posts (e.g., liking, sharing, commenting).2. Promotion on social media makes me more likely to visit an F&B business.3. I am more influenced by online recommendations and ads than traditional ads (TV, radio, print).4. I'm more likely to visit an F&B business when I see online promotions.5. Using digital marketing gives me more trust in an F&B business.6. I am more likely to purchase from an F&B business after seeing its promotions on social media.7. I am more likely to visit an F&B business if it has a strong online presence.	Konar et al. (2020)

Although all constructs were treated reflectively in this study, some items especially consumer preferences and marketing influence, may include items that function more like formative indicators. These items represent various aspects such as trust, behaviour, and attention, which together contribute to the overall construct. Reflective modelling was applied to maintain consistency and follow standard practices in PLS-SEM commonly used in exploratory research.

4.3. Statistical Analysis Techniques Used

This study utilises Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM) as the primary statistical analysis technique, implemented through the SMARTPLS software. Data for the analysis was gathered through a structured, quantitative survey to identify trends and evaluate hypotheses relating to the significance of digital and traditional marketing for e-businesses in Brunei.

This study used PLS-SEM because it is well-suited for analysing complex models with small sample sizes, a common limitation in business marketing research, particularly in contexts like Brunei. As noted by Guenther et al. (2023), PLS-SEM can still provide robust estimation results under limited sample conditions, making it a practical choice when large-scale data collection is challenging.

5. Data Analysis and Result

5.1 Sample Characteristics

Table 2 presents the demographic profile of the respondents, covering four main dimensions: age, education, dining frequency at F&B outlets in Brunei, and interaction with marketing platforms. A total of 99 respondents contributed to this study. The data shows that most respondents fall within the 18-27 age range (52.5%), followed by those aged 28-43 (26.3%). Respondents aged 44-59 constitute 20.2%, while only 1% are 60 years and above.

In terms of education, nearly half of the respondents (48.5%) have a Bachelor's degree. This is followed by those with a Master's degree (25.3%) and a Diploma (10.1%). Smaller groups hold an HND (6.1%), PhD (3%), or other types of qualifications (7%). When asked about their dining habits at F&B outlets in Brunei, the majority dine occasionally (37.4%) or frequently (30.3%). Fewer respondents dine very frequently (18.2%), while 14.1% dine rarely.

Regarding digital marketing engagement, Instagram is the most popular platform for discovering F&B businesses (89.9%), followed by TikTok (70.7%) and WhatsApp (38.4%). Other platforms like Facebook (26.3%), Google Ads (8.1%), and YouTube (7.1%) are less frequently used. For traditional marketing channels, radio is the most noticed platform (70.7%), followed by billboards (53.5%) and flyers (29.3%). TV (30%) and newspapers (18.2%) are also noted, while magazines are the least noticed (5.1%).

These findings offer valuable insights into the demographic characteristics and marketing platform preferences of respondents within the F&B sector.

Table 2. *Demographic profile of respondents*

Demographic Variables	Frequency (N)	Percentage (%)
Age		
18-27	52	52.5
28-43	26	26.3
44-59	20	20.2
60 and above	1	1
Education		
Diploma	10	10.1
HND	6	6.1
Bachelor's Degree	48	48.5
Master's Degree	25	25.3
PhD	3	3
Other	7	7
How often do you dine at F&B outlets in Brunei?		
Rarely	14	14.1
Occasionally	37	37.4
Frequently	30	30.3
Very Frequently	18	18.2
Which of the following digital marketing platforms do you engage with the most for discovering F&B businesses?		
Facebook	28	26.3
Instagram	89	89.9
TikTok	70	70.7
Google ads	8	8.1
WhatsApp	38	38.4
YouTube	7	7.1
Other	1	1
Which of the following traditional marketing platforms do you notice most often?		
TV	30	30
Radio	70	70.7
Newspapers	18	18.2
Magazines	5	5.1
Billboards	53	53.5
Flyers	29	29.3
Other	1	10

5.2 Validation and Reliability of Measurements

The reliability and validity analysis for the constructs indicated that most items met the typical factor loading threshold of 0.7. Ten items with factor loadings below the recommended 0.70 threshold were removed: PI3, PI4, PI5, IDTM4, IDTM5, BA1, BA2, TM6, CS2, and CS4. However, some items with loadings close to 0.5, such as CS4 (0.453) and DM3 (0.473), were retained. According to research by Hair et al. (2018), factor loadings as low as 0.4 are acceptable in some cases, so these items were kept to ensure a comprehensive representation of each construct. While efforts were made to include multiple items per construct, certain constructs in Marketing Effectiveness and Brand Awareness included only two items due to survey length limitations and threshold. Although this may affect the scale’s comprehensiveness, internal consistency measures were within acceptable thresholds, and similar approaches have been supported in prior literature (Bergkvist & Rossiter, 2007).

Table 3. *Validity and Reliability*

Variables	items	FL	α	CR	AVE	VIF
Marketing Effectiveness			0.612	0.727	0.72	
	ME1	0.84				1.24
	ME2	0.857				1.24
Consumer Satisfaction			0.692	0.789	0.515	
	CS2	0.61				1.341
	CS3	0.86				1.813
	CS4	0.453				1.246
	CS5	0.862				1.802
Brand Awareness			0.717	0.876	0.779	
	BA3	0.9				1.455
	BA4	0.865				1.455
Influence Marketing on purchase intention			0.644	0.786	0.485	
	PI1	0.608				1.139
	PI2	0.835				1.445
	PI3	0.55				1.206
	PI4	0.756				1.351
Digital Marketing (Consumer Preference)			0.776	0.848	0.536	
	DM1	0.773				1.751
	DM4	0.793				1.925
	DM3	0.473				1.217

Traditional Marketing (Consumer Preference)	DM4	0.822				1.953
			0.85	0.859	0.532	
	TM1	0.726				1.703
	TM2	0.566				1.402
	TM3	0.847				2.461
	TM4	0.745				1.977
	TM5	0.755				1.774
	TM6	0.747				2.058
	TM7	0.687				1.692

Note: N = 99; FL: Factor loading; α : Cronbach's alpha; CR: Composite reliability; AVE: Average variance extracted (AVE); VIF: Variance inflation factor.

To assess reliability, Cronbach's alpha was used, which evaluates the consistency of each item in a set measuring the same construct shown in Table 3 in Validity and Reliability, Values ranged from 0.612 to 0.850, with most constructs nearing the recommended 0.7 threshold, indicating satisfactory internal consistency. Composite Reliability (CR), which is similar to Cronbach's alpha but assigns greater weight to each item's factor loading, ranged from 0.727 to 0.876, further supporting the reliability of the constructs.

Average Variance Extracted (AVE) was also assessed; it indicates whether the items for each construct share sufficient common variance. An AVE above 0.5 is ideal, as it suggests that over half of the variance in the items is explained by the construct itself. Most constructs met this criterion, confirming "convergent validity." The AVE for Consumer Satisfaction was slightly above 0.5, at 0.515, suggesting that it captures sufficient variance. Finally, Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) values were all below 3, indicating that the constructs do not overlap excessively, thereby avoiding significant multicollinearity issues. Multicollinearity assesses whether constructs are too similar and might be measuring the same concept, which would compromise the analysis. Overall, the constructs demonstrate strong reliability and validity for an exploratory study, despite a few items with lower factor loading.

Table 4. Discriminant Validity – HTMT

	BA	CS	PI	ME	DM	TM
BA						
CS	0.592					
PI	0.255	0.586				
ME	0.362	0.341	0.256			
DM	0.288	0.783	0.937	0.26		
TM	0.697	0.609	0.225	0.461	0.235	

Note: N = 99, BA: Brand Awareness, CS: Consumer satisfaction, PI: Purchase intention, ME: Marketing Effectiveness, DM: Digital Marketing (Consumer Preferences), TM: Traditional Marketing (Consumer Preferences).

To assess discriminant validity among the constructs in the study, both the HTMT Table 4 and the Fornell-Larcker criterion Table 5 were used, each employing different methods to evaluate construct distinctiveness. The HTMT analysis was conducted to evaluate the distinctiveness of the constructs. In Table 4, most constructs demonstrated adequate discriminant validity, with HTMT values below the 0.85 threshold. However, the HTMT value for Digital Marketing (DM) and Intention to Purchase (IP) was 0.937, suggesting potential overlap. This indicates that DM and IP may be measuring similar concepts. Future research might refine these constructs to reduce overlap and improve discriminant validity.

Table 5. Discriminant Validity– Fornell and Larcker criterion

	BA	CS	PI	ME	DM	TM
BA	0.882					
CS	0.479	0.707				
PI	0.172	0.412	0.719			
ME	0.225	0.244	0.11	0.823		
DM	0.219	0.56	0.743	0.179	0.702	
TM	0.547	0.521	-0.007	0.316	0.162	0.786

Note: N = 99, BA: Brand Awareness, CS: Consumer satisfaction, PI: Purchase intention, ME: Marketing Effectiveness, DM: Digital Marketing (Consumer Preferences), TM: Traditional Marketing (Consumer Preferences).

Table 5, The square roots of the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) for each construct (shown on the diagonal of the matrix) were compared with the correlations between constructs. The square root of AVE measures how much variance is explained by each construct’s indicators, and for discriminant validity, it should be greater than the correlations between constructs. The results indicate that the constructs exhibit adequate discriminant validity, as the square root of the AVE for each construct exceeds its correlations with other constructs.

Overall, the results from both the HTMT ratio and the Fornell-Larcker criterion suggest that the constructs used in this study exhibit good discriminant validity, confirming that they are distinct and not highly collinear. Future research might refine constructs showing potential overlap to further improve discriminant validity.

Table 6. Coefficient of determination and cross-validated redundancy

	R2	Adj R2
DM	0.633	0.618
TM	0.410	0.391

Note: R2: coefficient of determination; Adj R2: adjusted coefficient of determination, DM: Digital Marketing (Consumer Preference), TM: Traditional Marketing (Consumer Preference).

Table 6 shows Digital Marketing (DM) has a high R² value of 0.633, indicating that approximately 63.3% of the variance in DM is explained by the model. The Adjusted R² value of 0.618 shows a slightly adjusted measure considering the number of predictors in the model. Traditional Marketing (TM) has a lower R² of 0.410, meaning that 41% of the variance in TM is explained by the model. The Adjusted R² of 0.391 provides a similar assessment, slightly accounting for model complexity.

Table 7. Test of direct effects

	Original Sample (O)	Sample mean	Standard deviation (STDEV)	t-values	P values	Significant level
H1a: ME → DM	0.305	0.304	0.089	3.446	0.001	Significant
H1b: ME → TM	0.037	0.034	0.102	0.369	0.712	Not Significant
H2a: PI → DM	0.660	0.666	0.074	8.940	0.000	Significant
H2b: PI → TM	-0.161	-0.157	0.099	1.623	0.105	Not Significant
H3a: CS → DM	0.008	0.004	0.082	0.092	0.927	Not Significant
H3b: CS → TM	0.533	0.543	0.104	5.132	0.000	Significant
H4a: BA → DM	-0.015	-0.015	0.073	0.200	0.841	Not Significant
H4b: BA → TM	0.304	0.309	0.109	2.789	0.005	Significant

The direct effects test examined how the independent variables: Marketing Effectiveness, Purchase Intention, Consumer Satisfaction, and Brand Awareness influence Digital Marketing (DM) and Traditional Marketing (TM). The results showed that Marketing Effectiveness significantly affects Digital Marketing, with a coefficient of 0.305 and a p-value of 0.001, meaning that as Marketing Effectiveness increases, Digital Marketing improves. However, Marketing Effectiveness did not have a significant effect on Traditional Marketing, with a coefficient of 0.037 and a p-value of 0.712.

Purchase Intention had a strong positive effect on Digital Marketing, with a coefficient of 0.660 and a p-value of 0.000, indicating that higher Purchase Intention improves Digital Marketing. But it did not significantly affect Traditional Marketing, with a coefficient of -0.161 and a p-value of 0.105. While Consumer Satisfaction did not impact Digital Marketing, with a coefficient of 0.008 and a p-value of 0.927, but it did positively influence Traditional Marketing, with a coefficient of 0.533 and a p-value of 0.000.

Lastly, Brand Awareness had no effect on Digital Marketing, with a coefficient of -0.015 and a p-value of 0.841, but it significantly influenced Traditional Marketing, with a coefficient of 0.304 and a p-value of 0.005.

Table 8. Summary of Hypothesis Results

Hypothesis	Variable	Coefficient (B)	p-value	Result
H1	Marketing effectiveness (digital vs. traditional) influences consumer preferences.			
H1a	Digital marketing effectiveness positively influences preferences for digital platforms.	0.305	0.001	Supported
H1b	Traditional marketing effectiveness positively influences preferences for traditional platforms.	0.037	0.712	Not Supported
H2	The influence of marketing on purchase intention affects consumer preferences.			
H2a	Influence of digital marketing on purchase intention positively influences preferences for digital platforms.	0.66	0.000	Supported
H2b	Influence of traditional marketing on purchase intention positively influences preferences for traditional platforms.	-0.161	0.105	Not Supported

H3	Consumer satisfaction with marketing significantly influences consumer preferences.			
H3a	Consumer satisfaction with digital marketing positively influences preferences for digital platforms.	0.008	0.927	Not Supported
H3b	Consumer satisfaction with traditional marketing positively influences preferences for traditional platforms.	0.533	0.000	Supported
H4	Brand awareness from marketing strategies significantly influences consumer preferences.			
H4a	Brand awareness through digital marketing positively influences preferences for digital platforms.	-0.015	0.841	Not Supported
H4b	Brand awareness through traditional marketing positively influences preferences for traditional platforms.	0.304	0.005	Supported

The study found that some hypotheses were supported, while others were not. For instance, Marketing Effectiveness did not affect Traditional Marketing, and Purchase Intention had no impact on Traditional Marketing. This suggests that other factors may be influencing these relationships. Future research could explore these connections further.

6. Findings and Discussions

It was identified through quantitative approach that for digital marketing engagement, Instagram is the most popular platform for discovering F&B businesses (89.9%), followed by TikTok (70.7%) and WhatsApp (38.4%). Other platforms like Facebook (26.3%), Google Ads (8.1%), and YouTube (7.1%) are less frequently used. As for traditional marketing channels, radio is the most noticed platform (70.7%), followed by billboards (53.5%) and flyers (29.3%). TV (30%) and newspapers (18.2%) are also noted, while magazines are the least noticed (5.1%).

Among the variables considered, marketing effectiveness has a positive influence on consumer's preference on digital marketing. However, the effectiveness of traditional marketing has not had a significant impact on traditional marketing channels. These findings demonstrate that digital marketing reaches more consumers and are more appealing than traditional marketing because of how interactive and personalised it is for consumers (Mehmeti-Bajrami, 2022; Singh & Bisaria, 2024). It is also consistent with the TAM model, which states that consumer's perceptions

of the ease of use and usefulness of digital marketing platforms play an important role in consumer preferences. Findings suggest that in Brunei, when most F&B businesses are trying to successfully attract their target audience, it is recommended that such companies consider more digital marketing methods such as social media and online advertising in their marketing communications so that they can easily stimulate purchase intention. The personalisation and interaction provided by digital marketing which helps increase consumer engagement and satisfaction (Singh & Basaria, 2024).

That digital marketing has a positive impact on consumer preferences on the influence of marketing on purchase intention affects consumer preferences more than traditional marketing. These findings are consistent with previous research that noted that the role of digital marketing is increasing especially among young audiences (Chen & Low, 2020). The results also support the TAM model and ET model, which argue that interaction through technology increases consumer satisfaction. This is because most consumers currently prefer marketing that is more interactive, provides data-backed context, and real time communications because consumers value it (Chaffey & Smith, 2017).

Following the analysis, consumer satisfaction with traditional marketing has a more positive influence on consumer preferences for traditional platforms than consumer satisfaction with digital marketing for digital platforms. Previous study also showed traditional marketing remains essential because it relies on physical presence to establish consumer trust, especially in culturally distinct settings like Brunei, where they may favour familiar and non-digital interactions (Kotler et al., 2019). To enhance consumer satisfaction and foster long-term loyalty, Brunei F&B companies need to understand consumer preferences between digital and traditional marketing formats.

As for the last hypothesis, brand awareness through traditional marketing has a more positive influence on consumer preferences for traditional platforms than brand awareness through digital marketing for digital platforms. Similar to the previous study by Qaderi (2022), which indicates that while digital brand awareness efforts on social media helped improve brand recognition, they do not consistently lead to a preference for digital channels. Traditional media like billboards or in-store promotions proved more effective in building long-term loyalty, even though advertisements did boost awareness among younger audiences. These findings support the idea that consumers favour traditional marketing channels for regular brand engagement (Ali Karam and Saydam, 2015). For F&B businesses in Brunei, combining traditional and digital marketing approaches could be beneficial in enhancing brand awareness across diverse demographics.

7. Conclusions

As shown from the findings, the independent variables identified in this research could be refined more specifically to cater to the F&B sectors. The study revealed that some hypotheses were supported and while others were not. Digital marketing was found to enhance brand awareness and purchase intention through consumer engagement, whereas traditional marketing strengthens consumer trust and long-term loyalty. F&B businesses in Brunei can combine their marketing efforts by leveraging and utilising the strengths of both digital and traditional marketing strategies. By following this balanced approach, businesses can enhance their competitive advantage, sustain long-term consumer relationships and adapt hopefully effectively to the evolution of marketing in the future.

While this research focused on how digital and traditional marketing affect consumer behavior in Brunei's F&B sector, some of the constructs, especially consumer preferences could be improved in future studies by using a formative structure. This would help capture more specific dimensions of how people make decisions based on different types of media exposure.

8. Limitations and Future Work

Due to limited literature in this developing field, there are gaps in understanding the subtle differences between digital and traditional marketing. As for the findings, it only focuses on Brunei specifically and may not be able to be applied to other regions with different consumer behaviour and cultural factors.

One of the limitations of this study is that some constructs, such as digital and traditional consumer preference, may not be purely reflective in nature. The items used include different reactions like trust, awareness, and behavioural intention, which could have been modeled formatively. Due to the time and scope of the project, a reflective model was used. Future studies can explore the same constructs using a formative approach for more precise measurement.

Future research could investigate these connections in greater depth. With the data gathered, this research can be targeted to an even more defined participants as the sample size may not fully represent Brunei's F&B consumer base which potentially impacts the study's generalisability. More variables could be explored in this research and used to approach through quantitative or qualitative methods which can be tailored to specific marketing channels such as Instagram, through TVs or

newspapers which can hopefully provide valuable insights for F&B businesses in selecting the most effective marketing strategies even more.

References

- Ahamat, A., Shahkat Ali, M.S., Azami, M.A., Prasad, N.V. (2022), Innovation Marketing from the Perspective of New Technologies in the Food and Beverage Industry, *Journal of Marketing Research and Case Studies*, Vol. 2022, pp. 2, <https://doi.org/10.5171/2022.492387>
- Ahmad, S.Z., & Omar, R. (2021). Digital marketing strategies and consumer engagement: Insights from F&B businesses in Southeast Asia. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 35(2), 150-167.
- Akar, E., & Topçu, B. (2011). An examination of the factors influencing consumers' attitudes toward social media marketing. *Journal of Internet Commerce*, 10(1), 35–67.
- Alalwan (2018): Alalwan, A. A. (2018). Investigating the impact of social media advertising features on customer purchase intention. *International Journal of Information Management*, 42, 65–77.
- Ali Karam, A., & Saydam, S. (2015). An Analysis Study of Improving Brand Awareness and Its Impact on Consumer Behavior Via Media in North Cyprus (A Case Study of Fast Food Restaurants). *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 6(1), 66–80.
- Anas, A. M., Abdou, A. H., Hassan, T. H., Alrefae, W. M. M., Daradkeh, F. M., El-Amin, M. A.M. M., Kegour, A. B. A., & Alboray, H. M. M. (2023). Satisfaction on the driving seat: Exploring the influence of social media marketing activities on followers' purchase intention in the restaurant industry context. *Sustainability*, 15(9), 7207. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15097207>
- Antczak, B. O. (2024). The influence of digital marketing and social media marketing on consumer buying behavior. *Journal of Modern Science*, 56(2): 310-335. 10.13166/jms/189429
- Authority for Info-communications Technology Industry. (2019). *Brunei Darussalam: Household ICT survey report 2019*. Retrieved from <https://www.aiti.gov.bn/surveys/bruneidarussalam-ict-business-report-2019/>
- Batra, R., & Keller, K. L. (2016). Integrating marketing communications: New findings, new lessons, and new ideas. *Journal of Marketing*, 80(6), 122–145. 10.1509/jm.15.0419
- Bergkvist, L., & Rossiter, J. R. (2007). The Predictive Validity of MultipleItem versus SingleItem Measures of the Same Constructs. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 44(2), 175–184. JSTOR. <https://doi.org/10.2307/30162466>
- Bist, A.S., Agarwal, V., Aini, Q., Khofifah, N., (2022), Managing Digital Transformation in Marketing: “Fusion of Traditional Marketing and Digital Marketing”, *International Transactions on Artificial Intelligence*, Vol. 1, pp. 18-19, <https://doi.org/10.33050/italic.v1i1.86>
- Billore, A., & Sath, A. (2015) Mobile advertising: A review of the literature. *The Marketing Review*, 15(2), 161-183. Doi: 10.1362/146934715X14373846573586
- Bojkov, K. (2024). 50 marketing survey questions and marketing surveys examples. *EmbedSocial*. Retrieved from September 26, 2024. <https://embedsocial.com/blog/marketing-surveyquestions/>

- Bukhowa, B., Alhalwachi, L., Alkhater, N., Taqi, N., Burshaid, B., & Danish, F. (2024). The impact of digital marketing on customer purchase decisions: The moderating influence of brand equity. In *Studies in Systems, Decision and Control* (pp. 351–369). Springer Nature Switzerland.
- Cesaroni, F.M., & Consoli, D. (2015). Are small businesses really able to take advantage of social media? *Electronic Journal of Knowledge Management*, 13(4), 257-268.
- Chaffey, D., & Smith, P. R. (2017). *Digital marketing excellence: Planning, optimizing and integrating online marketing*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315640341>
- Chen, L., & Low, J. (2020). The effectiveness of Traditional marketing in a digital age: Evidence from Brunei's F&B industry. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Marketing*, 12(3), 45-62.
- Duffett, R. G. (2017). Influence of social media marketing communications on young consumers' attitudes. *Young Consumers*, 18(1), 19–39. 10.1108/YC-07-2016-00622
- Evangelidis, I., Bhatia, S., Levav, J., & Simonson, I. (2024). 50 years of context effects: Merging the behavioral and quantitative perspectives. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 51(1), 19–28. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jcr/ucad028>
- Grewal, D., Roggeveen, A. L., & Nordfält, J. (2018). The future of retailing. *Journal of Retailing*, 94(1), 1–6. 10.1016/j.jretai.2016.12.008
- Gongora, M. O. (2016). Study of the factors influencing the adoption of social media in SMEs [Master's thesis]. Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya. Retrieved from <https://upcommons.upc.edu/bitstream/handle/2117/88058/TFM%20%20MARTA%20ORTEGA%20Document%201-Report%20and%20Annexes.pdf>
- Guenther, P., Guenther, M., Ringle, C. M., Zaefarian, G., & Cartwright, S. (2023). Improving PLS-SEM use for business marketing research. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 111, 127–142. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indmarman.2023.03.010>
- Ismaeel, B., & Alsariera, W. (2023). The effect of marketing effectiveness, and consumer behaviour on consumer purchase preference for Unilever products in Jordan. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 13(7). <https://doi.org/10.6007/ijarbss/v13-i7/17416>
- Jaman, S. F. I. H., Damit N. J. H., Ishak, N. A., Ason, M. L., Tamin, M. R., Tangphadungrutch, K., & Almunawar, M. N. (2020). The adoption of social media as marketing tools: Case small and medium enterprises in Brunei Darussalam. *International Journal of Asian Business and Information Management*, 11(2), 29-31, 41-44.
- Kalmegh, Prof. G.S., (2022), Digital Marketing Vs Traditional Marketing- A Comparative View, *International Journal of Research in Engineering and Science*, Vol. 10, pp 35.
- Konar, Rupam & Balasubramanian, Kandappan & Kumar, Jeetesh. (2020). The Impact of Social Media on Consumers' Purchasing Behaviour in Malaysian Restaurants - *Journal of Spatial and Organizational Dynamics*. 8. 197-216.
- Kotler, P., Kartajaya, H., & Setiawan, I. (2019). *Marketing 4.0: Moving from traditional to digital*. Wiley.
- Lee, M., & Musa, N. (2021). Traditional marketing in rural Brunei: Challenges and opportunities for F&B brands. *Journal of Consumer Research in Southeast Asia*, (4), 201-217.
- Mehmeti-Bajrami, S., Qerimi, F., & Qerimi, A. (2022). The impact of digital marketing vs. Traditional marketing on consumer buying behavior. *HighTech and Innovation Journal*, 3(3), 326–340. <https://doi.org/10.28991/hij-2022-03-03-08>
- Mkansi, M. (2020). E-business adoption costs and strategies for retail micro businesses.

- International Journal of E-Commerce*, 14(2),111-130. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10660-020-09448-7>
- Pappas, N. (2016). Marketing strategies, perceived risks, and consumer trust in online behaviour. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 29, 92–103. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2015.11.007>
- Qaderi, A. (2022). Impact of Online Advertisement and Brand Awareness on Consumers“ Buying Behavior: A Case Study of Istanbul. *International Journal of Science and Research (IJSR)*, 11(7), 1539–1546. <https://doi.org/10.21275/SR22718181544>
- Rosário, A., & Raimundo, R. (2021). Consumer marketing strategy and e-commerce in the last decade: A literature review. *Journal of Theoretical and Applied Electronic Commerce Research*, 16(7), 3003–3024. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jtaer16070164>
- Sama, Ramzan. (2019). Impact of Media Advertisements on Consumer Behaviour. *Journal of Creative Communications*. 14. 097325861882262. 10.1177/0973258618822624.
- Sharma, D. (2021). Transition from Traditional Marketing To Digital Marketing: A Bibliometric Analysis. *Academy of Marketing Studies Journal*, Vol. 25(3S), pp. 1–6.
- Singh, A. K., & Bisaria, C. (2024). Evolving dynamics: A comparative analysis of digital marketing and traditional marketing strategies in reshaping brand customer relationships. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Commerce, Management & Social Science (IJARCMSS)* , 7(01(II)), 163–169. <https://www.inspirajournals.com/uploads/Issues/284820644.pdf?form=MG0AV3>
- Sinha, R., (2018), A Comparative Analysis of Traditional Marketing Vs Digital Marketing, *Raj Sinha Journal of Management Research and Analysis*, Vol. 5(4), pp. 234.
- Solomon, M. R., Dahl, D. W., White, K., Zaichkowsky, J. L., & Polegato, R. (2018). Consumer behavior: Buying, having, and being (12th ed.). *Pearson*.
- Tan, W. H., Mokhtar, R., & Hadi,A. (2022). Consumer behavior and traditional marketing in Brunei: Insights from F&B businesses. *Brunei Journal of Marketing*, 15(3),123-139.
- Yasmin, A., Tasneem, S., Fatema, K., (2015), Effectiveness of Digital Marketing in the Challenging Age: An Empirical Study, *International Journal of Management Science and Business Administration*, Vol. 1, pp 69-72, DOI: 10.18775/ijmsba.1849-5664-5419.2014.15.1006
- Yuliantoro et al. (2019a): Yuliantoro, G., Suryani, T., Purwanegara, M. S., & Dharmmesta, B. S. (2019). The effect of social media influencer on brand image, self-concept, and purchase intention. *Journal of Management Science*, 5(2), 124–135.
- Yuliantoro, N., Goeltom, V., Juliana, I. B., Pramono, R., & Purwanto, A. (2019b). Repurchase intention and word of mouth factors in the millennial generation against various brands of Boba drinks during the Covid 19 pandemic. *African Journal of Hospitality, Tourism and Leisure*, 8(2), 1-11.
- Zain, M., & Rosli, M. (2021). Digital marketing versus traditional marketing: Comparative effectiveness in Brunei’s F&B sector. *Journal of Digital Business*, 8(1), 34-5